

Physico-Chemical Investigations on Polysaccharides from the Seeds of *Phaseolus aconitifolius* and *Phaseolus riccardianus*

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Physico-chemical investigations were carried out on the polysaccharides from the seeds of *Ph. aconitifolius* and *Ph. riccardianus*. By successive extraction process under identical conditions eight different fractions were isolated from each species. The third and eighth fractions isolated by extraction with hot water and 1.0 N sodium hydroxide solution were further purified and sub-fractionated. All the sub-fractions contained glucose, galactose and arabinose as component units. Periodate oxidation studies were carried out on them. The acetylated derivative of the third fraction was used in determining various macromolecular parameters by viscosity and light scattering methods for comparing the physico-chemical characteristics of the polysaccharides from these seeds of different species of the same genus.

SEEDS of different species belonging to the same genus may be easily differentiated on the basis of morphological features such as size, shape, colour, weight etc. The synthesis of polysaccharide which is a product of plant metabolism, is known to be genetically controlled and so the composition of the polysaccharides in the seeds of the same genus is expected to have certain intrinsic similarities. It is, therefore, of interest to study whether the species to species differences are reflected in the polysaccharides belonging to different species of the same genus.

In order to find out if there is any basis for such assumption, two species *Phaseolus aconitifolius* and *Phaseolus riccardianus* are chosen for a comparative study. They belong to the sub-family *Papilionaceae* of the family *Leguminaceae*. The differences in shape, size, colour and general appearance of the seeds are the least in these two species. This communication concerns the macromolecular characterisation of polysaccharide components from these two species. Important components identified in various parts of *Ph. aconitifolius* are starch¹, fatty acids², proteins³ and amino acids⁴; no such study has yet been reported on the seeds of *Ph. riccardianus*.

Eight different fractions of polysaccharides were isolated from the defatted and deproteinised seeds of each species as reported earlier⁵. First and second fractions were isolated from cold water extract, third and fourth from hot water extract, fifth and sixth from 0.1N sodium hydroxide extract and seventh and eighth from 1.0N sodium hydroxide extract. Ash and moisture percentages, specific

rotations and ratios of sugar components are given in Table 1.

As third and eighth fractions of both the species were in major quantities they were used in these studies. These polysaccharides were further purified and all the fractions contained glucose, galactose and arabinose as component sugars. On electrophoresis in borate buffer these fractions migrated towards anode in two bands whereas no movement was observed in phosphate buffer indicating that the polysaccharides were neutral and contained two substances. One of the components was starch as indicated by blue colour with iodine solution. On treatment with diastase the starch component was removed. The remaining material contained lower amount of glucose and failed to give colour for starch. On electrophoresis they moved as single substance; the ratios of sugar components *viz.*, galactose, glucose and arabinose are given in Table 2.

The enzyme-treated polysaccharides were further fractionated from their aqueous solution. Four fractions (O_{2A}-O_{2D}, etc.) were collected at different concentrations of ethanol (Table 3). The first sub-fraction of *Ph. riccardianus* had high specific rotation and contained more glucose. Iodine test for starch was positive. Some starch might have adhered to other polysaccharide as a result of which it escaped the action of enzyme. During this fractionation this portion was separated. The remaining three fractions having the same characteristics were mixed together for further studies. In the case of *Ph. aconitifolius* no significant differences were observed; they were mixed together. Purified third and eighth fractions of polysaccharides from these two seeds were considered homogeneous and their characteristics are given in Table 4.

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TABLE 1. PROPERTIES AND COMPOSITION OF THE POLYSACCHARIDE FRACTIONS FROM *Ph. aconitifolius* (O) AND *Ph. riccardianus* (R)

Polysaccharide fractions	Yield in % with respect to whole seed	Ash %	Moisture %	Specific* rotation	Ratio of sugar components			
					ga**	glu	ar	xy
O ₁	0.30	Nil	4.4	+121°	0.5	5.0	1.0	trace
O ₂	0.15	0.1	7.3	+137°	0.5	5.0	1.0	trace
O ₃	4.00	0.2	5.2	+119°	0.4	6.0	1.0	0.1
O ₄	0.10	0.2	10.2	+127°	0.5	6.0	1.0	0.1
O ₅	0.60	0.1	8.1	+113°	0.4	5.0	1.0	trace
O ₆	3.80	0.3	7.5	+138°	0.5	7.0	1.0	trace
O ₇	0.60	0.1	5.5	+114°	0.4	5.0	1.0	0.2
O ₈	3.30	0.2	6.4	+131°	0.5	8.0	1.0	0.2
R ₁	0.40	0.1	4.3	+43°	1.0	4.0	1.0	—
R ₂	0.20	Nil	4.2	+39°	1.0	3.5	1.0	—
R ₃	7.80	0.2	7.5	+157°	0.5	10.5	1.0	trace
R ₄	0.10	0.2	8.1	+77°	0.4	8.0	1.0	trace
R ₅	5.20	0.2	4.5	+147°	0.4	10.5	1.0	—
R ₆	4.20	0.3	6.6	+63°	0.5	4.0	1.0	0.2
R ₇	0.80	0.3	9.2	+71°	0.5	6.0	1.0	0.2
R ₈	13.80	0.2	6.2	+148°	0.4	12.0	1.0	0.2

* Conc. 0.5% in 0.5N sodium hydroxide solution

** ga—galactose; glu—glucose; ar—arabinose; xy—xylose.

TABLE 2. PROPERTIES AND COMPOSITIONS OF THE DIASTASE-TREATED 3RD AND 8TH FRACTIONS

Polysaccharide fraction	Specific rotation	*No. of spots on electrophoresis in borate buffer	Ratios of sugar components		
			ga	glu	ar
O ₃	+43°	one (+)	0.4	4.0	1.0
O ₈	+35°	one (+)	0.4	5.0	1.0
R ₃	+68°	one (+)	0.5	7.5	1.0
R ₈	+61°	one (+)	0.4	7.0	1.0

* +ve sign indicates movement towards anode.

 TABLE 3. SPECIFIC ROTATION AND RATIOS OF SUGAR COMPONENTS OF THE SUBFRACTIONS A, B, C, AND D OF POLYSACCHARIDES O₃, O₈, R₃ AND R₈

Polysaccharide fraction	Ethanol added %	Specific rotation	Ratios of sugar components		
			ga	glu	ar
O _{3A}	12.0	+39°	0.4	4.0	1.0
O _{3B}	35.0	+37°	0.5	4.0	1.0
O _{3C}	60.0	+40°	0.4	4.0	1.0
O _{3D}	90.0	+38°	0.4	4.0	1.0
O _{8A}	15.0	+34°	0.4	4.5	1.0
O _{8B}	40.0	+35°	0.5	5.5	1.0
O _{8C}	65.0	+36°	0.4	5.0	1.0
O _{8D}	88.0	+33°	0.4	5.0	1.0
R _{3A}	10.0	+123°	0.4	12.0	1.0
R _{3B}	40.0	+42°	0.4	6.0	1.0
R _{3C}	75.0	+40°	0.4	6.5	1.0
R _{3D}	92.0	+43°	0.4	6.0	1.0
R _{8A}	12.0	+124°	0.4	10.0	1.0
R _{8B}	30.0	+35°	0.4	6.0	1.0
R _{8C}	50.0	+35°	0.5	6.0	1.0
R _{8D}	88.0	+38°	0.4	6.0	1.0

The four purified fractions of polysaccharides from these two species of seeds were subjected to periodate oxidation studies. The periodate uptake and the formic acid liberation during the reaction were measured at intervals and the final results are given in Table 4.

To study the size and shape of these macromolecules the purified third fraction from each species was chosen because of its high yield. They were converted to acetylated derivatives having almost same acetyl content. These acetylated products of polysaccharides from *Ph. aconitifolius* and *Ph. riccardianus* are named as fraction "O" and fraction "R" respectively. The intrinsic viscosities of fractions O and R in chloroform solution were 1.53 dl/g and 1.22 dl/g respectively.

Light scattering studies were carried out on these acetylated fractions. The weight-average molecular weight, \bar{M}_w , was determined first by dissymmetry method using Debye equation⁵. On plotting Hc/τ against concentration, c , a straight line was obtained which on extrapolation to zero concentration gave the value for $1/\bar{M}_w$. The values of \bar{M}_w for fractions O and R were calculated to be 1.300×10^7 and 1.195×10^7 respectively. The dissymmetry function, Z , for each dilution was calculated from the ratio of $I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$. The intrinsic dissymmetry, $[Z]$, was determined by extrapolating the measured values of Z to zero concentration. In practice Z was not a linear function of concentration but when $1/Z-1$ was plotted against c , a straight line was obtained. $[Z]$ was found to be 2.613 and 2.776 for fractions O and R respectively. The reciprocal of the particle scattering factor, $1/P(\theta)$ corresponding to $[Z]$ was obtained from standard tables⁶, by assuming the shape of the polysaccharide molecules to be polydisperse coils and rods. In the case of fraction, O, $1/P(\theta)$ values for polydisperse coils and for rods

TABLE 4. SPECIFIC ROTATION, SUGAR COMPONENTS AND PERIODATE OXIDATION RESULTS OF HOMOGENEOUS FRACTIONS O₃, O₆, R₃ AND R₆

Polysaccharide fraction	Specific rotation	Ratios of sugar components			Moles of periodate consumed per mole of anhydro hexose	Moles of anhydro hexose units liberating one mole of formic acid
		ga	glu	ar		
O ₃	+40°	0.4	4.0	1.0	1.50	4.0
O ₆	+36°	0.4	5.0	1.0	1.45	3.6
R ₃	+42°	0.4	6.0	1.0	1.60	3.3
R ₆	+38°	0.4	6.5	1.0	1.60	3.3

were 2.69 and 4.08 respectively and for fraction R the corresponding values were 2.98 and 4.64 respectively. Hence the corrected weight-average molecular weights of fraction O for rod-shaped and coil-shaped particles were calculated to be 5.297×10^7

are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The value of the arbitrary constant, k, was taken to be 500. From the grid-like plot the two limiting lines, $(Kc/R_\theta)_{c \rightarrow 0}$ and $(Kc/R_\theta)_{\theta \rightarrow 0}$, on extrapolation met at the same point on the ordinate. This value, $(Kc/R_\theta)_{c \rightarrow 0, \theta \rightarrow 0}$

FIG. 1 ZIMM PLOT FOR EXTRAPOLATION OF LIGHT SCATTERING DATA OF PH. ACONITIFOLIUS
 ●...RESULTS OF EXTRAPOLATION AT CONSTANT θ TO $c \rightarrow 0$
 ▲...RESULTS OF EXTRAPOLATION AT CONSTANT c TO $\theta \rightarrow 0$

and 3.489×10^7 respectively; the corresponding values for fraction R were 5.545×10^7 and 3.560×10^7 respectively.

The weight-average molecular weight was also determined by Zimm's method. Scattering was measured at different angles (30° - 100°) for different concentrations. Zimm plots of Kc/R_θ vs $(\text{Sin}^2\theta/2 - kc)$

was equal to the reciprocal of the weight-average molecular weight and the corresponding \bar{M}_w values for fractions O and R were calculated to be 3.450×10^7 and 3.534×10^7 respectively. These results were in good agreement with those obtained by dissymmetry method assuming the shape of the particles to be polydisperse coils.

FIG. 2. ZIMM PLOT FOR EXTRAPOLATION OF LIGHT SCATTERING DATA OF PH. RICCARDIANUS

FIG. 3. THE LIMITING LINE $(Kc/R_θ)_{c \rightarrow 0}$ OF ZIMM PLOT AT LOWER ANGLES
 O---- R (PH. RICCARDIANUS)
 Δ---- O (PH. ACONITIFOLIUS)

FIG. 4. THE LIMITING LINE $(Kc/R\theta)_{c \rightarrow 0}$ OF ZIMM PLOT AT HIGHER ANGLES

●--- PH. ACONITIFOLIUS (O)
 Δ--- PH. RICCARDIANUS (R)

A tangent was drawn to the limiting curve of $(Kc/R\theta)_{c \rightarrow 0}$ vs $\text{Sin}^2\theta/2$ at lower angles near the point of its intercept to $Kc/R\theta$ axis (Fig. 3) and a suitable asymptote was drawn at higher angles at the limiting curve of the Zimm plot (Fig. 4). The slope and intercept of the tangents and those of the asymptotes were evaluated. Assuming that the particles obey Gaussian and random flight statistics for the randomly coiling chains, number-average

molecular weight, (\bar{M}_n) , z-average and number-average root-mean-square values of radius of gyration, $(\sqrt{\bar{\rho}^2})$, and end-to-end distance, $(\sqrt{\bar{r}^2})$, of the polysaccharide particles were calculated. The results are shown in Table 5.

where $\phi = 2.1 \times 10^{21}$ by using intrinsic viscosity results. The discrepancy in these results obtained from light scattering and intrinsic viscosity data can be explained in the light of the limitations of the Flory-Fox equation to a highly extended randomly coiled chain as this equation with $\phi = 2.1 \times 10^{21}$ may not hold good due to the stiffness of the polysaccharide chains.

The ratio of weight-average molecular weight to number-average molecular weight, \bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n , is a measure of polydispersity. The high value of this ratio in the case of these two polysaccharides indicates an extremely wide and skewed molecular weight distribution and such a result is also expected for molecules having randomly placed branches.

TABLE 5. MACROMOLECULAR PARAMETERS OF THE ACETYLATED POLYSACCHARIDE FRACTIONS FROM *Ph. aconitifolius* (O) AND *Ph. riccardianus* (R)

Parameter	<i>Ph. aconitifolius</i>	<i>Ph. riccardianus</i>
\bar{M}_w	3.450×10^7	3.534×10^7
$\sqrt{\bar{\rho}^2}$	2651 Å	2628 Å
$\sqrt{\bar{r}^2}$	6492 Å	6436 Å
\bar{M}_n	1.351×10^6	1.563×10^6
$\sqrt{\bar{\rho}_n^2}$	24.9 Å	24.8 Å
$\sqrt{\bar{r}_n^2}$	61.0 Å	60.7 Å
\bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n	25.5	22.6
$\sqrt{\bar{R}^2}$	995 Å	968 Å

The effective root-mean-square end-to-end distance, $\sqrt{\bar{R}^2}$, of the polysaccharide molecule was calculated from the Flory-Fox equation^{6a}, $(\bar{R}^2)^{3/2} = \bar{M}_n[\eta]/\phi$,

Chemical analysis shows that the polysaccharide fractions from these two seeds contain glucose, galactose and arabinose, the former one being predominant. Starch is one of the components. On purification, a polysaccharide fraction having almost same specific rotation and same ratio of component sugars was obtained from both the seeds. Periodate oxidation studies tentatively suggest similar nature of linkages and branch points. These two polysaccharide fractions have molecular weights of the same order. Being considerably branched, viscosity and light scattering data suggest certain degree of stiffness in both the molecules as indicated by end-to-end distance and radius of gyration; the molecular parameters agree with characteristics of coils rather than rods. These results point out the intrinsic similarities between some polysaccharide components obtained from the seeds of these two species of the same genus. However, there are other fractions with varying proportions of sugar components and obviously more work is needed to isolate them as pure components and to study their molecular architecture.

Experimental

Paper partition chromatography was carried out by descending technique. The solvent was allowed to run against the machine line. Whatman No. 1 and No. 3 mm filter papers were used, the latter for separating larger quantities of sugar mixtures. TLC experiments were performed using 1 mm thick kieselguhr-G coated glass plates. The following solvent systems (v/v) were used for both types of chromatography :—

- (A) ethyl acetate : pyridine : water (8 : 2 : 1);
- (B) ethyl acetate : pyridine : water (2 : 1 : 2);
- (C) *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5) upper layer;
- (D) *n*-butanol : ethanol : water (5 : 1 : 4) upper layer;
- (E) ethyl acetate : pyridine : acetic acid : water (5 : 5 : 1 : 3).

Reducing sugars were located on chromatograms by spraying with (1) alkaline silver nitrate solution and (2) saturated solution of aniline oxalate in water. All specific rotations were of equilibrium values. Unless otherwise stated all evaporations were carried out *in vacuo* at 30°–40°.

Isolation and purification of the polysaccharide :

The seeds were freed from outer skins, macerated, defatted⁷, deproteinised⁸ and different fractions of polysaccharides were isolated according to the scheme as described earlier⁹. Different polysaccharide fractions were isolated from the two species of seeds under exactly identical conditions. The powdered material (*Ph. aconitifolius*, 20 g. and *Ph. riccardianus*, 28 g.) was extracted successively with (1) cold water, (2) boiling water, (3) 0.1*N* sodium hydroxide solution and (4) 1.0*N* sodium hydroxide solution. In the case of water extractions two fractions could be isolated from each of the extracts; the first fraction was precipitated by adding 1/3 volume of ethanol and the second one with about three volumes to the supernatant obtained after removing the first fraction. Alkali extract was acidified to pH 5.0 with acetic acid when some material precipitated out. This was removed at the centrifuge and ethanol (ca. 3 volumes) was added to the clear solution to precipitate the next fraction. Thus eight polysaccharide fractions were isolated from the seeds of *Ph. aconitifolius* and were designated as O₁, O₂, O₃, O₄, O₅, O₆, O₇ and O₈ respectively. The corresponding fractions from the seeds of *Ph. riccardianus* were named as R₁ to R₈. The yields of different fractions are given in Table 1.

All the fractions were purified by repeated precipitation. The material (1 g.) was dissolved in water (200 ml.) at boiling water bath temperature, cooled and then centrifuged. Ethanol was added to the clear supernatant to precipitate the polysaccharide. This process was repeated thrice.

Identification and estimation of sugars :

The polysaccharide (200 mg.) was hydrolysed by heating with 2*N* sulphuric acid (2.5 ml.) on a boiling

water bath for 18 hr. The solution was neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered and the solution was concentrated to a syrup. The hydrolyzate was examined by paper chromatography and TLC and in all cases glucose, galactose, arabinose and traces of xylose were detected.

The polysaccharide (200 mg.) was hydrolysed with 2*N* sulphuric acid in a sealed tube. Ribose was added as an internal reference and the hydrolyzate was neutralised, filtered, concentrated and the solution was made upto a known volume (2.0 ml.). A portion of it (0.2 ml.) was separated by paper chromatography quantitatively into its constituent sugars and the zones corresponding to each sugar were marked with guide spots. These were cut, eluted with water (5.0 ml.) and the amount of each monosaccharide was determined by periodate oxidation method¹⁰. In a second experiment the eluted monosaccharides were estimated colorimetrically by different colour reactions. Table I shows the mean values of these estimations and other physical characteristics of different fractions.

Electrophoresis of the polysaccharide :

The third and eighth fractions were subjected to electrophoresis using silica gel plates and borate (pH, 9.5) and phosphate (pH, 7.5) buffers; a potential gradient of 10 volts per cm was used. The spots were detected by spraying with concentrated sulphuric acid. In borate buffer all the fractions gave two spots whereas no movement was observed in phosphate buffer. The polysaccharides gave blue colour, characteristic of starch, with iodine solution.

Enzymic degradation :

The polysaccharide (1 g.) was dispersed in an acetate buffer (pH 4.6, 400 ml.) and then incubated with 10 mg. of diastase (*Aspergillus oryzae*) at 37° for 72 hr. The solution failed to give iodine test for starch. After keeping at 80° for 15 min. to deactivate the enzyme, the solution was dialysed for three days against distilled water, concentrated and lyophilised. Ratio of sugar components and specific rotation of the isolated materials are given in Table 2.

Fractionation of polysaccharides :

The enzyme-treated materials were fractionally precipitated from their aqueous solutions (1 g./200 ml.) by gradual addition of ethanol. Four fractions (O_{3A} to O_{3D} etc.) were collected in each case. The results of fractionation, specific rotation value and the ratio of component sugars of each sub-fraction are given in Table 3. The sub-fractions of O₃ and O₈ were mixed up separately and the last three sub-fractions of R₃ and R₈ were also similarly mixed up; the resulting four materials were used in further investigations.

Periodate oxidation studies :

The polysaccharide (40.0 mg.) was dissolved in water (50.0 ml.) and sodium meta periodate solution (0.1*M*, 50.0 ml.) was added to it. The reaction was allowed to proceed in dark at 25°. Periodate consumption and formic acid liberation were determined

at regular intervals by the method of Fleury and Lange^{11, 12}. The results are given in Table 4.

Acetylation of the polysaccharide :

Two grams each of the third fractions of purified, enzyme-treated and then fractionated polysaccharides, O and R, were dried at 60° in *vacuo* for 4 hr and then dispersed in dry distilled formamide (20 ml.). It was then acetylated¹³ by the addition of pyridine (25 ml.) and acetic anhydride (20 ml.). The acetylated product was precipitated by adding the reaction mixture to ice cold water, filtered through a sintered glass filter, washed, triturated with absolute alcohol and then dried in *vacuo* at 60°. It was once again acetylated in the same way. The percentage of acetyl content was determined. Acetyl content : fraction O, 44.2% and fraction R, 43.8%.

Viscosity measurements :

The viscosity of the acetylated polysaccharide was measured in a Ubbelohde Viscometer at 30° in chloroform solution at eight different concentrations ranging between 0.080 and 0.805 g/ml. The intrinsic viscosity was determined graphically by extrapolation of reduced viscosity, η_{sp}/c , to zero concentration.

Light scattering measurements :

The acetylated polysaccharide fractions O and R were used for light scattering measurements. Chloroform, twice distilled in all glass apparatus under dust-free conditions, was further clarified by passing through a sintered glass (G-5) and was used as solvent. A stock solution (0.5%) of the acetylated polysaccharide in chloroform was clarified by passing through a sintered glass (G-4) twice under dust-free conditions. The concentration of the filtered solution was again determined by dry weight method. From the stock solution seven solutions of different concentrations over a range of 0.187 to 2.840 mg/ml.

were prepared by dilution. The concentration of each solution was once again checked by dry weight method.

Intensities of light scattered by different solutions were measured with "Brice Phoenix" light scattering photometer Model-OM1000A, according to the procedure described by Brice¹⁵ *et al.* Green light ($\lambda = 5461 \text{ \AA}$) was used throughout the experiment. The weight-average molecular weight was determined by dissymmetry method¹⁶ using a semioctagonal cell and by Zimm¹⁷ method by using a cylindrical cell.

References

1. M. H. QUERESHJI, *Pakistan J. Sci. Research*, 1949, 2, 63.
2. A. S. BROWN and J. C. GOUB, *Indian J. Appl. Chemistry*, 1960, 23, 157.
3. M. TAKAHAZA and J. C. RIPPERTON, *Hawaii Agr. Expt. Sta. Bull.*, 1949, 100, 5.
4. P. D. DESHPANDE and M. V. R. RAO, *Indian J. Med. Research*, 1954, 42, 77.
5. P. DEBYE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1947, 51, 18.
6. K. A. STACEY, *Light Scattering in Physical Chemistry*, Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1955.
- 6a. P. J. FLORY and T. G. FOX, *J. Polymer. Sci.*, 1950, 5, 745.
7. T. E. TIMMEL, *Tappi*, 1961, 44, 88.
8. E. L. HIRST, J. K. N. JONES and W. O. WALDER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1227.
9. A. K. CHAKRABORTY and C. V. N. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 1055.
10. E. L. JACKSON, *Organic Reactions*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1944, Vol. 2, p. 341.
11. P. FLEURY and J. LANGE, *J. Pharm. Chim.*, 1933, 17, 107.
12. F. BROWN, T. G. HALSALL, E. L. HIRST and J. K. N. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 27.
13. A. L. POTTER and W. Z. HASSID, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3774.
14. J. B. NIEDERL and V. NIEDERL, *Methods of Quantitative Organic Analysis*, 2nd edition, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1948, p. 252.
15. B. A. BRICE, M. HALWER and R. SPEISER, *J. Opt. Soc. Amer.*, 1950, 40, 768.
16. P. DEBYE, *J. Phys. and Colloid Chem.*, 1947, 51, 18.
17. B. H. ZIMM, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, 16, 1093, 1099.